

THE PROBLEM OF LIPSCHITZ CONDITION

Marcela Popescu and Paul Popescu
University of Craiova, Department of Mathematics
13, A.I. Cuza st., Craiova, 1100, Romania

In our paper we prove that the Smarandache function S does not verify the Lipschitz condition, giving an answer to a problem proposed in [2] and we investigate also the possibility that some other functions, which involve the function S , verify or not verify the Lipschitz condition.

Proposition 1 *The function $\{n \rightarrow S(n)\}$ does not verify the Lipschitz condition, where $S(n)$ is the smallest integer m such that $m!$ is divisible by n . (S is called the Smarandache function.)*

Proof. A function $f : M \subseteq R \rightarrow R$ is Lipschitz iff the following condition holds:

$$(\exists) K > 0, (\forall) x, y \in M \Rightarrow |f(x) - f(y)| \leq K |x - y|$$

(K is called a Lipschitz constant).

We have to prove that for every real $K > 0$ there exists $x, y \in N^*$ such that $|f(x) - f(y)| > K |x - y|$.

Let $K > 0$ be a given real number. Let $x = p > 3K + 2$ be a prime number and consider $y = p + 1$ which is a composite number, being even. Since $x = p$ is a prime number we have $S(p) = p$. Using [1] we have $\max_{n \in N^*, n \neq 4} \{S(n)/n\} = 2/3$, then $\frac{S(y)}{y} = \frac{S(p+1)}{p+1} \leq \frac{2}{3}$ which implies that $S(p+1) \leq \frac{2}{3}(p+1) < p = S(p)$. We have

$$|S(p) - S(p+1)| = p - S(p+1) \geq p - \frac{2}{3}(p+1) > \frac{3K+2-2}{3} = K$$

■

Remark 1. The idea of the proof is based on the following observations:

If p is a prime number, then $S(p) = p$, thus the point $(p, S(p))$ belongs to the line of equation $y = x$;

If q is a composite integer, $q \neq 4$, then $\frac{S(q)}{q} \leq \frac{2}{3}$ which means that the point $(q, S(q))$ is under the graphic of the line of equation $y = \frac{2}{3}x$ and above the axe $\overline{Ox}$.

Thus, for every consecutive integer numbers x, y where $x = p$ is a prime number and $y = p - 1$, the length AB can be made as great as we need, for x, y sufficiently great.

Remark 2. In fact we have proved that the function $f : N^* \rightarrow N$ defined by $f(n) = |S(n) - S(n - 1)|$ is unbounded, which imply that the Smarandache's function is not Lipschitz.

In the sequel we study the Lipschitz condition for other functions which involve the Smarandache's function.

Proposition 2 The function $S_1 : N \setminus \{0, 1\} \rightarrow N$, $S_1(n) = \frac{1}{S(n)}$ verify the Lipschitz condition.

Proof. For every $x \geq 2$ we have $S(x) \geq 2$, therefore $0 < \frac{1}{S(x)} \leq \frac{1}{2}$. If we take $x \neq y$ in $N \setminus \{0, 1\}$, we have

$$\left| \frac{1}{S(x)} - \frac{1}{S(y)} \right| \leq \frac{1}{2} \leq \frac{1}{2} |x - y|.$$

For $x = y$ we have an equality in the relation above, therefore S_1 is a function which verify the Lipschitz condition with $K = \frac{1}{2}$ and more, it is a contractant function.

Remark 3. In [2] it is proved that $\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{1}{S(n)}$ is divergent .

Proposition 3 The function $S_2 : N^* \rightarrow N$, $S_2(n) = \frac{S(n)}{n}$ verify the Lipschitz condition.

Proof. For every $x, y \in N$, $1 < x < y$ we have $x = n$ and $y = n + m$ where $m \in N^*$. In [2] is proved that

$$\frac{1}{(n-1)!} \leq \frac{S(n)}{n} \leq 1, (\forall)n \in N \setminus \{0, 1\}.$$

Using this we have

$$\left| \frac{S(x)}{x} - \frac{S(y)}{y} \right| = \left| \frac{S(n)}{n} - \frac{S(n+m)}{n+m} \right| \leq 1 - \frac{1}{(n+m-1)!} < 1 \leq |x-y|$$

therefore

$$\left| \frac{S(x)}{x} - \frac{S(y)}{y} \right| \leq |x-y|$$

for x and y as above. For $x = y$ we have an equality in the relation above. It follows that S_2 is verify the Lipschitz condition with $K = 1$. ■

Remark 4. Using the proof of *Proposition 5* proved below, it can be shown that the Lipschitz constant $K = 1$ is the best possible. Indeed, take $x = n = p - 1$, $m = 1$ and therefore $y = p$ (with the notations from the proof of *Proposition 3*), with p a primenumber. From the proof of *Proposition 5*, there is a subsequence of prime numbers $\{p_{n_k}\}_{k \geq 1}$ such that $\frac{S(p_{n_k}-1)}{p_{n_k}-1} \xrightarrow{k \rightarrow \infty} 0$. For $k \geq 1$ we have, for a Lipschitz constant K of S_2

$$K \geq \left| \frac{S(p_{n_k})}{p_{n_k}} - \frac{S(p_{n_k}-1)}{p_{n_k}-1} \right| = 1 - \frac{S(p_{n_k}-1)}{p_{n_k}-1} \xrightarrow{k \rightarrow \infty} 1$$

Thus, $K \geq 1$

Proposition 4 The function $S_3 : N \setminus \{0, 1\} \rightarrow N$, $S_3(n) = \frac{n^2}{S(n)}$ does not verify the Lipschitz condition.

Proof. (Compare with the proof of Proposition 1.)

We have to prove that for every real $K > 0$ there exists $x, y \in N^*$ such that $|S_3(x) - S_3(y)| > K|x - y|$.

Let $K > 0$ be a given real number, $x = p$ be a prime number and $y = p - 1$. Using the Proposition 5 proved below, which asserts that the sequence $\left\{ \frac{p_n - 1}{S(p_n - 1)} \right\}_{n \geq 2}$ is unbounded (where $\{p_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is the prime numbers sequence), we have, for a prime number p such that $\frac{p-1}{S(p-1)} > K + 1$:

$$\left| \frac{x}{S(x)} - \frac{y}{S(y)} \right| = \left| \frac{p}{S(p)} - \frac{p-1}{S(p-1)} \right| = \frac{p-1}{S(p-1)} - 1 > K + 1 - 1 = K = K|x - y|$$

■

Proposition 5 If $\{p_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is the prime numbers sequence, then the sequence $\left\{ \frac{p_n - 1}{S(p_n - 1)} \right\}_{n \geq 2}$ is unbounded.

Proof. Denote $q_n = p_n - 1$ and let r_n be the number of the distinct prime numbers which appear in the prime factor decomposition of q_n , for $n \geq 2$. We show below that $\{r_n\}_{n \geq 2}$ is an unbounded sequence.

For a fixed $k \in N^*$, consider $\pi_k \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} p_1 \cdots p_k$ and the arithmetic progression $\{1 + \pi_k \cdot m\}_{m \geq 1}$. From the Dirichlet Theorem [3, pg.194], it follows that this sequence contains a subsequence $\{1 + \pi_k \cdot m_i\}_{i \geq 1}$ of prime numbers: $p_{n_i} = 1 + \pi_k \cdot m_i$, therefore $\pi_k \cdot m_i = p_{n_i} - 1 = q_{n_i}$ which implies that $r_{n_i} \geq k$. It shows that the sequence $\{r_n\}_{n \geq 2}$ is an unbounded sequence.

If $q_n = \prod_{i=1}^{r_n} p_{\beta_i}^{\alpha_i}$ then it is known (see [4]) that:

$$S(q_n) = \max_{i=1, r_n} \left\{ S(p_{\beta_i}^{\alpha_i}) \right\} = S(p_{\beta_j}^{\alpha_j}) \leq \alpha_j p_{\beta_j},$$

thus

$$\frac{q_n}{S(q_n)} = \frac{\prod_{i=1}^{r_n} p_{\beta_i}^{\alpha_i}}{S(p_{\beta_j}^{\alpha_j})} \geq \left(\prod_{i=1, i \neq j}^{r_n} p_{\beta_i}^{\alpha_i} \right) \frac{p_{\beta_j}^{\alpha_j - 1}}{\alpha_j}. \quad (1)$$

We have:

$$u_j = \frac{p_{\beta_j}^{\alpha_j - 1}}{\alpha_j} \geq 2 \quad (2)$$

Indeed, if $\alpha_j = 1$, then $u_j = 1$. If $\alpha_j > 1$, then

$$u_j \geq \frac{(p_j - 1)(\alpha_j - 1)}{\alpha_j} \geq \frac{p_j - 1}{2} \geq \frac{1}{2}$$

But $v_n = \prod_{i=1, i \neq j}^n p_{\beta_i}^{\alpha_i}$ has $r_n - 1$ prime factors and $\{r_n\}_{n \geq 2}$ is unbounded, then it follows that $\{v_n\}_{n \geq 2}$ is unbounded. Using this, (1) and (2), it follows that the sequence $\left\{ \frac{f_n}{S(q_n)} \right\}_{n \geq 2}$ is unbounded. ■

Remark 5. Using the same idea, the Proposition 5 is true in a more general form:

For $a \in \mathbb{Z}$, the sequence $\left\{ \frac{p_n + a}{S(p_n + a)} \right\}_{p_n + a \geq 2}$ is unbounded, where $\{p_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is the prime numbers sequence.

References

- [1] T. Yau *A problem of maximum*, Smarandache Function Journal, vol.4-5, No.1, September 1994, pg.45.
- [2] F. Smarandache *An infinity of unsolved problems concerning a function in the number theory*, Smarandache Function Journal, vol.1, No.1, December 1994, pg.18-66.
- [3] C Popovici *Teoria numerelor*, Editura didactică și pedagogică, București, 1973.
- [4] Păl Gronăs *A proof of the non-existence of SAMMA*, Smarandache Function Journal, vol.4-5, No.1, September 1994, pg.22-23.